

The electrochemical Na extraction/insertion of $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$

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ABSTRACT: A mixed valence $\text{V}^{+3}/\text{V}^{+4}$ composite material belonging to the $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}/\text{C}$ family was synthesized and the electrochemical Na extraction/insertion mechanism was determined using a combination of high-resolution synchrotron X-ray diffraction (XRD) data, X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS), ^{23}Na and ^{19}F solid state Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR), double titration (for the elucidation of the vanadium oxidation state) and electrochemical measurements. The vanadium oxidation state was found to be +3.8 for the as-prepared sample. Detailed cathode structural evolution illustrated that the $\text{V}^{+4}/\text{V}^{+5}$ couple is active in this compound during electrochemical cycling between 2.8 and 4.3 V. This study demonstrates how the sodium-ion extraction and insertion pathways in cathode materials can be followed (and verified) using a number of experimental techniques, especially when multiple potential oxidation states are present in the parent compound.

1. Introduction

There exists growing scientific and commercial interest in the sodium-ion battery technology. Recent studies on applicable voltage ranges, electrode/electrolyte stability and diffusion barriers of sodium-ion and lithium-ion battery materials indicate that sodium-ion systems can be competitive with lithium-ion systems [1]. This is mainly due to the natural abundance of sodium and its relatively lower price compared to lithium [2]. The search for commercially viable sodium-ion batteries demands finding and optimizing new electrode materials and electrolytes, in order to get more economic, safer and longer life batteries.

Framework materials based on the phosphate polyanion have been identified as potential electroactive materials for sodium metal and sodium ion battery applications due to the strong inductive effect of the PO_4^{3-} group. In particular, fluorophosphate materials possess even higher operating voltages, because the inductive effect of fluorine is added to the effect of phosphate [3]. The high operating voltages provide these cathode materials a key advantage to solve the energy density challenges of sodium-based batteries.

In sodium-vanadium fluorophosphates, the existence of a mixed valence family of compounds between $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_3$ and $\text{Na}_3(\text{VO})_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}$ phases has been recently reported by our research group [4] as well as by Park et al. [5]. Thus, $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_3$ and $\text{Na}_3(\text{VO})_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}$ represent extreme or end member compounds present in the +3

and +4 vanadium oxidation state respectively, whereas intermediate compounds are $\text{V}^{+3}/\text{V}^{+4}$ mixed valence phases. In the general formula $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ that we proposed ($x = 0$ for $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_3$ and $x = 1$ for $\text{Na}_3(\text{VO})_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}$) the vanadium oxidation state and, therefore, the fluorine and oxygen content (x value) varies according to the amount of remaining carbon in the material during synthesis [4]. $\text{Na}_3(\text{VO})_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}$ (V^{+4} phase) is obtained when there is no remaining carbon in the as-prepared sample. However, $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_3$ (V^{+3} extreme) seems to be unstable, irrespective of the carbon proportions used. This fact can be attributed to the oxidizing atmosphere present in the vessel used in hydrothermal method, where the carbon coating does not seem to be enough to affect the complete or partial oxidation of V^{+3} . A recent report concerning $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_3$ (V^{+3} phase) using a different synthetic regime illustrated that the electrochemical activity was attributed to $\text{V}^{+3}/\text{V}^{+4}$ redox reaction [6], but all mixed valence compounds studied to date indicate that the electroactive redox couple corresponds to $\text{V}^{+4}/\text{V}^{+5}$ [4]. In general, $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ sodium-vanadium fluorophosphates are good cathodic materials for Na-ion batteries due to their high reaction voltages (at 3.6 and 4.1 V vs. Na/Na^+) and their good specific capacity values and cyclability in sodium half-cells. Current findings indicate that a moderate carbon percentage (≈ 6 % wt.) and, hence, a $\text{V}^{+3}/\text{V}^{+4}$ mixed valence in the as-prepared cathodes enhances electrochem-

ical performance due to the intrinsically better conductivity [4]. Therefore, the $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ sample studied in this work is prepared by the hydrothermal method using a carbon-containing VPO_4 ceramic precursor resulting in a 6.4% wt. carbon in the final product [7]. However, no detailed structural work has been undertaken to determine the sodium extraction/insertion mechanism of these materials in light of their superior electrochemical performance. Additionally, the ambiguity in the electroactive vanadium oxidation states need to be resolved in order to design better compositions in this system. These aspects are addressed in this work, using information derived from several techniques including, high-resolution synchrotron X-ray diffraction (XRD), ^{23}Na and ^{19}F solid state Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR), double titration for the determination of the vanadium oxidation state, *ex situ* XRD data of charged and discharged electrodes at selected voltages, X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) and electrochemical measurements. These reveal the evolution of the vanadium oxidation state associated with the sodium-ion insertion/extraction and electrochemical properties in a sodium cell.

2. Experimental Section

$\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ was synthesized by the hydrothermal method from a ceramic precursor. The synthesis process took place in two steps. First, VPO_4/C composite was synthesized by the ceramic method. V_2O_5 (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.99% purity) and $\text{NH}_4\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$ (Fluka, 99.5% purity) were mixed in an agate mortar in a stoichiometric ratio with a 25% molar excess of Kejten black. This mixture was annealed twice under nitrogen atmosphere at 300 and 850° C. Second, sodium fluorophosphate sample was prepared under mild hydrothermal conditions at 170° C and autogenous pressure by reacting NaF (Sigma-Aldrich, 99% purity) and the VPO_4/C composite in a 3.3/1 molar proportion. The reaction mixture was sealed in a polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE)-lined steel pressure vessel, which was maintained at 170° C for 65 hours.

Elemental analysis was performed using an Eurovector 3000. Powder X-ray diffraction patterns were collected in a Bruker D8 Advance Vario diffractometer working with $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation at room temperature. High-resolution synchrotron XRD data were collected on the Powder Diffraction beamline (10-BM-1) [8] at the Australian Synchrotron using a wavelength (λ) of 0.83696(2) Å, determined using the NIST 660a LaB_6 standard reference material. Powder samples were packed and sealed in 0.5 mm glass capillaries and data were collected for 6 minutes at ambient temperature using Debye-Scherrer geometry. Rietveld refinements were carried out using the GSAS [9] software suite with the EXPGUI [10] software interface.

The ^{23}Na solid state Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (ssNMR) spectrum was recorded in a Bruker Avance III 500 spectrometer (11.7 Tesla magnet) using the standard 1.3 mm Bruker MAS probe. The spinning speed was set to 50 kHz at room temperature. A single pulse sequence was used, with 90° pulse duration of 1.3 μs and a recycle delay of 2 seconds. The ^{23}Na shift was referenced to 0.1 M NaCl (0 ppm). The ^{19}F spectra were recorded in a Bruker Avance

III 200 MHz spectrometer (4.68 Tesla) with 50 kHz MAS frequency in order to avoid interference with the rotational sidebands. A single pulse sequence was used, with 90° pulse duration of 2 μs and a recycle delay of 5 seconds. The ^{19}F shift was referenced to solid LiF (-204 ppm). The recycle delay in this case was set to 3 s.

The quantification of the average oxidation state of vanadium (AV) was done by a double titration method [5]. Vanadium-containing compounds were completely dissolved in a 2 M H_2SO_4 solution at 80° C. The first titration with the 0.1 N KMnO_4 solution was stopped when the overall color of the solution abruptly changed to red (corresponding to the complete oxidation of the unknown initial oxidation state $\text{V}^{+?}$ to V^{+5}) and the total volume of the KMnO_4 solution consumed during the first titration ($V1$) was measured. An excess amount of $\text{FeSO}_4(\text{NH}_4)_2(\text{SO}_4)\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was added to the solution to reduce all V^{+5} ions to V^{+4} ions by the $\text{Fe}^{+2}/\text{Fe}^{+3}$ redox couple. Afterwards, an excess amount of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ was added to fully oxidize residual Fe^{+2} to Fe^{+3} to ensure the accuracy of the second titration. The second titration with the 0.1 N KMnO_4 solution was stopped when the overall color of the solution abruptly changed to red (corresponding to the complete oxidation of V^{+4} to V^{+5}) and the total volume of the KMnO_4 solution consumed during the second titration ($V2$) was measured. Finally, the average oxidation state of vanadium (AV) was calculated by the equation “ $\text{AV} = 5 - V1/V2$ ”.

Concerning the electrochemical performance, the positive electrodes were manufactured by mixing 80% wt. active material, 10% wt. conductive carbon (Super C65, Timcal) and 10% wt. polyvinylidene fluoride binder (PVDF 5130, Solvay) dissolved in N-methylpyrrolidone. A few mL N-methylpyrrolidone (NMP) (Aldrich) were added and the resulting slurry was stirred for 1 h. This slurry was coated on aluminium foil using the “doctor blade” technique. The electrode film was dried at 80° C in a vacuum oven for 24 h. Circular electrodes were cut from the foil, pressed for better contact of the coated material and aluminium current collector, dried under vacuum overnight (120° C) and finally transferred to an argon-filled glove box (Jacomex). The mass loading of the electrodes was about 4 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$. Electrochemical measurements were performed using metallic sodium as counter electrode, glass microfiber (Whatman, GF/A) as separator and a 1M NaPF_6 in ethylene carbonate:dimethyl carbonate (EC:DMC, 1:1 by wt%) as electrolyte. The electrochemical cycling was performed using a Biologic VMP3 Multichannel potentiostat-galvanostat. Galvanostatic cycling was performed at C/20 rate stopping at different voltages between 2.8 and 4.3 V during charge and discharge to obtain the *Post Mortem* electrodes. The lattice parameter evolution of the extracted *Post Mortem* cathodes were determined using XRD data collected on the Bruker D8.

The evolution of vanadium oxidation state during charge/discharge process was followed by X-ray Absorption Near-Edge Spectroscopy (XANES) using cycled *Post Mortem* electrodes stopped at different steps of voltage during the electrochemical reaction. These experiments

were conducted on the XAFS beamline of the Elettra Synchrotron (Trieste, Italy). XANES data were collected at the vanadium K-edge (5465 eV) in transmission mode and at room temperature, with a step size of $\Delta E = 0.1$ eV for the edge region. Energy calibration was established by measuring simultaneously a vanadium foil inserted between the second and third ionization chambers. All the spectra were normalized by a standard procedure [11] using Athena analysis software [12]. XAS spectra of specifically prepared V^{+3} ($\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3 - V^{+3}$ standard) and V^{+4} ($\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F} - V^{+4}$ standard) standards were also measured for reference. These standards were prepared such that their structures were similar to that of the samples, in order to improve the XANES analysis. No standard with a structure resembling that of the samples could be obtained for V^{+5} .

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of raw mixed valence $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ sample:

The hydrothermal synthesis of $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ resulted in a black powder suggesting some carbon remains in the material after synthesis. This is confirmed by elemental analysis which shows that $6.4\% \pm 0.05$ wt. of carbon remains in the final product. The sample was examined by XRD, showing well-defined diffraction maxima, indicating a crystalline sample, with a small amount of unreacted VPO_4 initial precursor (See Figure 1). The diffraction pattern was indexed to a phase adopting $P4_2/mnm$ space group symmetry with lattice parameters: $a = 9.030(3)$ Å and $c = 10.644(7)$ Å, that is intermediate between the extreme compositions of the $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ family: $\text{Na}_3(\text{VO})_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}$ ($x=1$; $a = 9.03051(2)$ Å, $c = 10.62002(3)$ Å [13]) and $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_3$ ($x=0$; $a = 9.047(2)$ Å, $c = 10.705(2)$ Å [14]) phases. The use of Vegard's law to calculate the average vanadium oxidation state results in a value around $V^{+3.82}$.

Figure 1. Whole pattern matching of XRD data of the synthesized material. Experimental (red circles), fitted (black line) and difference between them (blue lower line).

To precisely determine the crystal structure of the as-synthesized material, high resolution synchrotron XRD data were collected. Rietveld refinements were undertaken with a number of structural models, and the starting model of Le Meins et al. [14] gave the best initial fit to the data. This model was modified to the synthetic composition, and

refined starting with the lattice followed by the atomic positional parameters. Next, the atomic isotropic displacements parameters were independently refined, and finally the occupancy of the two sodium crystallographic sites. A small amount of the VPO_4 secondary phase was also present in this sample and was modeled in $Cmcm$ space group with refined lattice parameters of $a = 5.2404(5)$, $b = 7.7782(7)$ and $c = 6.2858(6)$ Å. The phase fractions of VPO_4 : $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ were 2.1(6)% : 97.9(1)%. The final fit to the data is shown in Figure 2, refined structural details are presented in Table 1, and the structure is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Rietveld refined fit of the $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ model and synchrotron XRD data with the inset showing an enlarged $25 \leq 2\theta \leq 38^\circ$ region. Data are shown as crosses, the calculated Rietveld model as a line through the data, and the difference between the data and the model as the line below the data. The vertical reflection markers are for $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ (lower markers) and VPO_4 (upper markers).

Figure 3. The crystal structure of $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ with PO_4 shown in purple and VO_4F_2 in red. Oxygen is red, fluorine is light blue and sodium is yellow with the shading indicating occupancy.

Table 1. Refined crystallographic parameters for Na₃V₂O_{2x}(PO₄)₂F_{3-2x},

Atom	<i>x</i>	<i>y</i>	<i>z</i>	Site Occu- pancy Factor	Isotropic Atomic Displacement Parameter (× 100)/Å ²	Bond Valence Sum
Na(1)	0.5249(8)	0.2185(9)	0	0.973(11)	4.50(32)	0.94
Na(2)	0.7659(13)	0.0127(11)	0	0.547(9)	1.43(29)	1.10
V(1)	0.24776(23)	0.24776(23)	0.19503(10)	1	0.55(2)	3.36
P(1)	0	0.5	0.25	1	0.69(28)	4.52
P(2)	0	0	0.2556(7)	1	0.72(28)	5.23
O(1)	0.0925(7)	0.3980(8)	0.1597(10)	1	0.76(27)	2.06
O(2)	0.0946(8)	0.0946(8)	0.1644(16)	1	0.60(40)	2.16
O(3)	0.4003(8)	0.4003(8)	0.1723(16)	1	1.30(40)	2.13
F(1)	0.2489(8)	0.2489(8)	0	1	1.38(10)	1.25
F(2)	0.2504(7)	0.2504(7)	0.35865(33)	1	3.57(10)	1.24

These data suggest there is little exchange between the two Na sites. In other words, sodium-ions do not average out to 75% occupancy on the two available crystallographic sites (Na(1) and Na(2)), but rather one site (Na(1)) is fully occupied while the other site (Na(2)) is only half occupied. The Na(1) site shows a large isotropic atomic displacement parameter suggesting that the sodium-ions are weakly centered at this atomic site.

The distribution of F and O on the anionic sites is difficult to determine due to the very similar scattering factors of these atoms when X-ray diffraction data is used. Thus, the bond valence sum (BVS) approach [15][16] was employed, showing that the BVS for the F(1) and F(2) sites were close to 1, the expected value for F. Additionally the BVS for the O sites were found to be close to 2 in agreement with the BVS expected for O. However, there exists the possibility of anion disorder on these sites which would manifest as a larger atomic displacement parameter directed to the vanadium site due to the variation in bond lengths between V-O and V-F. The F(1) site is the corner connecting site for the two corner connected vanadium octahedra and shows the largest bond length between vanadium and any anion in this cathode. Thus the F(1) site is an unlikely site for anion disorder. The F(2) site is ‘open’ to the sodium-ion channels and shows a large isotropic atomic displacement parameter indicating F/O disorder on this site. Additionally, the V-F(2) bond length is significantly smaller than the other V-O and V-F bond lengths which suggests that some of the oxygen on this site is double bonded to vanadium. In fact, the V-F(2) distance, 1.741(4) Å, (see Table S1 from Supplementary Information) is intermediate between a single V-F bond (~2.1 Å in the V⁺³ extreme phase, end-member) and a double V=O bond (1.64 Å in the V⁺⁴ extreme phase, end-member), confirming the partial substitution of F by O. Calculations on the amount of F and O extrapolated from this bond length, and assuming only V=O and V-F bonds (i.e., no V-O bonds in V-F(2)), indicate a ratio 23% F and 77% O. This corresponds to 23%

V⁺³ and 77% V⁺⁴ and an average vanadium oxidation state of V^{+3.77}.

Figure 4 shows the ²³Na solid state NMR (ssNMR) spectrum of the mixed valence compound. Three main signals are present in the spectrum, which were fitted using the DMfit program [17]. The relative intensities of the resonances observed at 74 ppm, 111 ppm and 158 ppm amount to 72 %, 22 % and 6 % respectively. These shifts indicate the presence of hyperfine interactions between the ²³Na and the paramagnetic vanadium ions [18]. Hyperfine shifts are very sensitive to interatomic distances, bond angles and to the oxidation states of the paramagnetic centers and are usually reflected by very large chemical shift values. In our case, by close examination of the coordination sphere of the sodium we detect that each Na⁺ is in the vicinity of two equidistant vanadium ions as highlighted by the dashed lines in the figure. V⁺³ ions generally cause a more positive shift than V⁺⁴ by several tenths of ppms [5, 19], and their effect is additive. Based on these observations, we assign the three signals observed in the spectrum to the V⁺⁴-V⁺⁴ (74 ppm), V⁺³-V⁺⁴ (111 ppm) and V⁺³-V⁺³ (158 ppm) pairs. Considering the relative populations of the three pairs as obtained by the fittings of figure 4, we obtain an averaged oxidation state of the vanadium in the mixed phase of V^{+3.83}. For a completely random distribution of the vanadium oxidation states in a sample with an averaged oxidation state of +3.83, we would expect relative intensities of the V⁺⁴-V⁺⁴, V⁺³-V⁺⁴ and V⁺³-V⁺³ pairs of 69 %, 28 % and 3 % respectively. These values are very similar to the ones observed in our experiment. Here, the relative populations of the homogeneous pairs V⁺⁴-V⁺⁴ and V⁺³-V⁺³, are slightly favored respect to the intermediate V⁺³-V⁺⁴. It is conceivable that structural changes induced by the oxidation state of one vanadium can affect the stability of its neighbor.

Figure 4. ^{23}Na ssNMR of the mixed valence $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ phase. Lines of fit are also shown.

The ^{19}F ssNMR spectrum of the compound is shown in Figure 5. The best fitting of the signal was obtained by considering two Lorentzian functions centered at 109 and 94 ppm. Taking into account that the theoretical populations of the two distinct ^{19}F sites in the pure V^{+3} compound is 1:2 and the relative intensities of the two signals, we obtain a ratio of 80 % V^{+4} and 20 % V^{+3} in the mixed valence phase ($\text{V}^{+3.8}$ on average). The discrepancy between the composition of the phase obtained from the ^{19}F and ^{23}Na analyses is very small ($\text{V}^{+3.8}$ and $\text{V}^{+3.83}$) and is considered to be within the error of the fitting procedures. These values are consistent with those expected from a Vegard-type relationship and the high resolution synchrotron XRD data.

Figure 5. ^{19}F ssNMR spectrum of the mixed valence $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ phase. Lines of fit are also shown. The inset on the right hand side illustrates the atomic positions of some F atoms resulting in these shifts.

Table 2. Experimentally determined vanadium oxidation states for selected vanadium-containing compounds by the double titration method.

Sample	Theoretical oxidation state of vanadium	Experimental average oxidation state of vanadium (AV)
V_2O_3	+3	3.04
VO_2	+4	3.98
V_2O_5	+5	5
$\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$?	3.76
$\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F} - \text{V}^{+4}$ standard	+4	4.01

The initial vanadium oxidation state is crucial in interpreting the electrochemical Na extraction/insertion mechanism, thus another method was used to verify the vanadium oxidation state of the mixed valence sample - the double titration method as recently employed by Park et al. [5]. Moreover, different vanadium oxides (V_2O_3 , VO_2 and V_2O_5) and the $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F} - \text{V}^{+4}$ standard have been also analyzed in order to have reference standards for the mixed valence phase.

The results shown in Table 2, indicate that the mixed valence sample is composed of 76% V^{+4} and 24% V^{+3} . Although some VPO_4 impurity remains in the cathode, this can be accounted for and is approximately 2% from synchrotron XRD data so that the vanadium oxidation state for the $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ sample remains around $\text{V}^{+3.8}$ correlating well with the other analysis techniques. In light of those data we can propose $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{1.6}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{1.4}$ as the general formula for the as-synthesized material.

3.2. Study of post-mortem electrodes of $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ material:

We recently reported that the $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ sodium–vanadium fluorophosphates present excellent electrochemical properties such as high specific capacity near the theoretical value and excellent cyclability [4][6]. The electrochemical behaviour of the $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}/\text{C}$ composite has been investigated by galvanostatic cycling with periodic current interrupts (Figure 6). Prior to the cycling in GITT (Galvanostatic Intermittent Titration Technique) mode the material has been cycled for 3 cycles at C/20 between 2.8 - 4.3 V. The electrochemical charge-discharge curve presents two pseudo-plateaux of similar length at 3.6 and 4.1 V vs. Na/Na^+ . A discharge capacity of 98 mA h g^{-1} ($\approx 75\%$ of the theoretical capacity) is obtained and a low polarization has been observed. The shape of the electrochemical curve suggests that the electrochemical reaction occurs through single-phase mechanisms, e.g. sloping potential curve. Similar observations have been made Chihara et al., [20] and Shakoor et al. [6] who have investigated the electrochemical mechanism of sodium extraction/insertion from/into $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_3$. Both groups report that the electrochemical reaction occurs through single-phase mechanism with negligible ($\sim 2\%$) volume variation.

Figure 6. Galvanostatic cycle obtained in open circuit voltage conditions (C/20 rate, relaxation criteria: 2h). Black: experimental points. Red: curve rebuilt from relaxation points.

The structural evolution of cathode materials during sodium insertion/extraction is an indicator of the long term stability of the electrode, e.g. volume expansion/contraction, and performance or potential characteristics of the battery, e.g. solid-solution or two-phase mechanism of sodium insertion/extraction. Electrode-containing test cells were equilibrated at the potentials indicated in Figure 7 and extracted from these test cells for *Post Mortem* or *ex situ* XRD and XANES analysis.

Figure 7. Points during charge/discharge where *Post Mortem* electrodes were extracted for their analysis by XRD and XANES.

Table 3. Evolution of lattice parameters of the $\text{Na}_y\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ cathode during charge (C)/discharge (D).

	Sample	a (Å)	c (Å)
	Starting material	9.030(3)	10.644(7)
C	~ 3.6 V	9.02(1)	10.63(2)
	~ 3.65 V	8.95(2)	10.70(3)
	~ 3.8 V	8.92(1)	10.71(2)
	~ 4.1 V	8.914(6)	10.73(1)
	~ 4.3 V	8.910(4)	10.74(1)
D	~ 3.8 V	8.923(8)	10.71(1)
	~ 3.59 V	8.96(1)	10.68(2)
	~ 2.8 V	9.023(8)	10.63(1)

Ex situ XRD data collected on electrodes extracted from Swagelok cells may react with the atmosphere to produce new phases. Although contact with air was minimized, we noted the presence of $\text{Na}_{0.29}\text{VOPO}_4 \cdot 1.73\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in some extracted electrodes, especially the electrodes at higher states of charge. In addition, we also found minute quantities of AlF_3 , which is probably due to the corrosion of the Al current collector. Nonetheless, the major phase present in all extracted samples was $\text{Na}_y\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ and this was analyzed in terms of lattice parameters which are shown in Table 3 and Figure 8.

Figure 8. Lattice parameter evolution of $\text{Na}_y\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ during charge and discharge from XRD on *Post Mortem* electrodes where 1 to 9 on the x-axis refers to the points in the electrochemical charge/discharge curve shown in Figure 7

There is no evidence for two-phase behavior, e.g. reflection splitting, for any of these electrodes, in the equilibrated state. The reflections positions shift to different 2θ values indicating an expansion and contraction of the lattice, consistent with a solid-solution type structural evolution during charge/discharge. As shown in Table 3, the a lattice parameter decreases while c lattice parameter increases during charge. This process reverses during discharge. The overall lattice volume follows the same trend as the a parameter during charge/discharge. The changes in the a and c lattice parameters suggest that the tunnels in this structure evolve as shown in Figure 9 with sodium extraction during charge.

Figure 9. Evolution of the channel size with charging (sodium extraction).

To confirm the evolution of the sodium-ion tunnels in the crystal structure with charge/discharge, another electrode was equilibrated at point “4.1 V” during charge and high resolution synchrotron XRD data were collected. A similar approach to the as-synthesized cathode was used to analyse the sodium-extracted electrode and the fit of the structural model to the data is shown in Figure 10, crystallographic details presented in Table 4 and the structural model shown in Figure 11. The refined lattice parameters were $a = 8.92220(8)$ Å and $c = 10.74862(19)$ Å, correlating to the expectations from laboratory XRD data. Sodium content resulted to be 2.26, thus $y = 2.26$. The F(1)-F(1) and F(2)-

F(2) distances, 6.363(9) and 3.008(5) for the $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ sample and 6.3082(1) and 3.2940(1) for the *Post Mortem* sample, respectively, correspond to the vertical and horizontal dimensions of the tunnels (Figure 12), and these tunnels evolve as predicted from the XRD analysis of *Post Mortem* electrodes, so the hypothesis of the tunnels becoming smaller in the x and y direction and wider in z direction is confirmed.

Figure 10. Rietveld refined fit of the $\text{Na}_y\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ model where $y = 2.26(6)$ and synchrotron XRD data with the inset showing an enlarged $20 \leq 2\theta \leq 40^\circ$ region. Data are shown as crosses, the calculated Rietveld model as a line through the data, and the difference between the data and the model as the line below the data. The vertical reflection markers are for $\text{Na}_y\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ (lower markers) and VPO_4 (upper markers).

Figure 11. The crystal structure of a *Post Mortem* electrode charged up to 4.1 V. PO_4 shown in purple and VO_4F_2 in red. Oxygen is red, fluorine is light blue and sodium is yellow with the shading indicating occupancy. The central ions in the polyhedra are shown to indicate the orientation and displacements. Crystal axes are shown inset at the bottom left.

This *Post Mortem* synchrotron XRD data show some further noteworthy aspects. The phase fractions of $\text{VPO}_4:\text{Na}_{2.26(6)}\text{V}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_3$ are 10.2(2)% : 89.8(1)%, slightly different to the phase fractions of the original cathode. In other words, a smaller fraction of fluorophosphate phase is observed, which can arise due to the conversion of some of the fluorophosphate phase into an amorphous, nanocrystalline or disordered component with the oxidation process, and thus being undetectable with X-ray diffraction. Further, other reflections were present for this *Post Mortem* sample

that were not identified using a range of known structural models, and can be seen at $2\theta \sim 24$ and 31° in Figure 10.

Figure 12. Evolution of F1-F1 and F2-F2 distances (channel size) with charging (Na extraction) according to results derived from synchrotron XRD data.

The refined structural model shows highly distorted vanadium octahedra which may indicate some type of structural transformation may occur at a certain stage of sodium extraction. Importantly, these data indicate that sodium is extracted from the Na(1) site (at least until this state of charge) and may actually proceed via the Na(2) ‘out’ of the crystal structure. This is indicated by the $\sim 50\%$ reduction in site occupancy of the Na(1) site and the $\sim 16\%$ increase in site occupancy of the Na(2) site compared to the as-synthesized cathode. In other words, the sodium moves from the Na(1) site to the Na(2) site and then out of the structure. However, other possibilities may exist here, e.g. sodium extraction from both sites simultaneously, and a second process that transfers sodium from Na(1) to Na(2). Note, that the refined sodium content of $y = 2.26(6)$ is higher than the expected value from electrochemical considerations of $y = 1.51$. This could influence the above interpretation and the reasons for the differences in sodium content include cathode relaxation processes [21], cathode polarization, chemical side reactions with exposure to air and the overestimation of the sodium in the structural model due to the presence of extra unidentified phases.

High resolution synchrotron XRD data suggests that there is a difference in phase composition between the fresh and cycled electrodes with a significant decrease in the content of the major $\text{Na}_y\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ phase in cycled electrodes. One mechanism to account for this apparent decrease is the conversion of the major $\text{Na}_y\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ phase to shorter-range or amorphous phases (or even nano-crystals that are virtually undetectable by XRD) during charge. Additionally the higher than expected sodium content in the major $\text{Na}_y\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ phase determined from the cycled ex-situ high resolution synchrotron XRD data maybe due to this amorphous-like phase(s) containing significantly less sodium. The combination of the sodium contents of the amorphous-like and crystalline phases would result in the expected sodium content from the electrochemical process. Furthermore, the process of amorphization may be reversible during discharge as expected by the electrochemical curves, however, further work is required to determine the role of the changes in phase composition.

Table 4. Refined crystallographic parameters for $\text{Na}_{2.26(6)}\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$

Atom	x	y	z	Site Occu- pancy Factor	Isotropic Atomic Displacement Parameter ($\times 100$)/ \AA^2	Bond Valence Sum
Na(1)	0.5243(23)	0.2674(32)	0	0.491(19)	0.20(40) ^a	1.08
Na(2)	0.7956(20)	0.0554(20)	0	0.640(20)	0.20(40) ^a	0.92
V(1)	0.2478(7)	0.2478(7)	0.18610(27)	1	1.15(11)	3.98
P(1)	0	0.5	0.25	1	2.46(17) ^b	4.97
P(2)	0	0	0.2600(19)	1	2.46(17) ^b	3.71
O(1)	0.1181(13)	0.4161(11)	0.1722(13)	1	0.62(21) ^c	2.09
O(2)	0.0965(16)	0.0965(16)	0.1490(19)	1	0.62(21) ^c	1.92
O(3)	0.3934(16)	0.3934(16)	0.1611(18)	1	0.62(21) ^c	2.23
F(1)	0.2500(32)	0.2500(32)	0	1	4.45(26) ^d	1.26
F(2)	0.2398(20)	0.2398(20)	0.3468(9)	1	4.45(26) ^d	1.25

a, b, c, d constrained to be equal

The secondary phase, VPO_4 , has been modelled in $Cmcm$ space group with the following lattice: $a = 5.2342(4)$, $b = 7.7819(6)$ and $c = 6.2809(5)$ \AA

We have followed the evolution of the vanadium valence state during the charge/discharge process by means of XANES spectroscopy at the vanadium K-edge. This technique is sensitive to the oxidation state and to the local structure of the absorber element, in our case the vanadium atom. In a qualitative way, it is expected a shift in the edge position towards higher energies with increasing vanadium valence.

The XANES spectra of the *Post Mortem* samples at different stages of the electrochemical Na extraction/insertion reaction are displayed in Figure 13. The shape of the spectra changes during the charge/discharge process, as can be seen in the position of the pre-edge and white line features, which indicates changes in the vanadium environment, as revealed by XRD measurements, and in the vanadium valence state. The edge position and shape of the completely reduced sample (2.8V) is practically identical to the as-synthesized sample (starting $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$ sample named as ‘‘Raw’’), which indicates a complete reversibility of the charge/discharge process, at least in terms of the active vanadium oxidation states

The pre-edge feature has been assigned to a forbidden transition $1s \rightarrow 3d$ [22]. The intensity and position of this feature is related to the nature and symmetry of the vanadium ligands in the sample. Figure 14 presents the evolution of the pre-edge during the charge process, including $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3 - \text{V}^{+3}$ and $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F} - \text{V}^{+4}$ standards. Closer examination reveals the presence of a triplet structure, characteristic of octahedrally coordinated vanadium cations, lacking an inversion center [22]. A qualitative analysis of this region is the following: taking into account the pre-edges of our V^{+3} and V^{+4} standards, and that of V^{+5} standards according to references [23][24], contributions to the pre-edge zone can be assigned to V^{+3} (5468 eV), V^{+4} (5469.5 eV) and V^{+5} (5471 eV) with increasing energy, as marked with arrows in Figure 14. As observed, during the charge process, the first peak, lowest energy V^{+3} , is essentially constant. This appears to corroborate our hypothesis [4], that V^{+3} does not participate in the oxidation process.

Additionally, the second peak corresponding to V^{+4} decreases while the third peak corresponding to V^{+5} increases. This suggests that V^{+4} progressively oxidizes and converts into V^{+5} .

Figure 13. Vanadium K-edge XANES spectra of the samples during the charge (top) and discharge (bottom) process.

An estimation of the oxidation state of the raw sample can be made by fitting the pre-edge to a linear combination of the V^{+3} and V^{+4} standards [23][24]. This fitting indicates that there exists around 82% V^{+4} and 18% V^{+3} in the as-synthesized sample, which is in good agreement with the percentage estimated by XRD, NMR and the double titration method ($\sim 80\% V^{+4}$).

Figure 14. Vanadium K-edge pre-edge feature of the samples (continuous line) and the standards (dashed lines). Arrows indicate the position of the three characteristic peaks.

To shed more light on the evolution of the vanadium valence during the oxidation/reduction of the samples, the XANES spectrum of each sample has been fitted using a linear combination of the totally reduced (Raw) and totally oxidized (4.3 V) samples [25]. The valence state of the starting sample can be obtained by fitting the XANES region to a linear combination of the V^{+3} and V^{+4} standards (see Figure S2 from Supplementary information). This fitting indicates that there exists around 85% V^{+4} and 15% V^{+3} in the as synthesized sample, which is consistent with the percentage estimated by the fitting of the pre-edge ($\sim 82\% V^{+4}$) as well as by the rest of the techniques employed (XRD, NMR and double titration). Lacking a V^{+5} standard, the average oxidation state of vanadium of the 4.3 V sample was roughly estimated from the electrochemical curve, and found to be 75.4% of oxidized material corresponding to a $V^{+4.53}$ valence.

Figure 15. XANES spectra of the 3.9 V sample, and the corresponding fit to a linear combination of Raw and 4.3 V XANES profiles (LCF).

An example of the fitting procedure and results is illustrated in Figure 15 showing a relatively straightforward approach with an acceptable fit. In this way, the relative amount of each component (e.g. vanadium oxidation state distribution) in all intermediate states can be determined.

Table 5 gathers the percentage of the two spectra used for the fittings, the estimated vanadium valence deduced from the electrochemical curves for each post-mortem cathode, and the vanadium valence calculated from the fitting of the spectra. The XANES results show that during the cathode oxidation, the average vanadium valence progressively increases from $V^{+3.8}$ to $V^{+4.5}$, and the process is completely reversible. Since the amount of V^{+3} is practically constant during the reaction, we can propose the following reaction:

Therefore, at the end of the reaction, nearly all the V^{+4} oxidizes to V^{+5} , while the V^{+3} does not participate in the reaction.

Table 5. Percentage of the two spectra used for the fitting, the estimated vanadium valence obtained from the electrochemical curves for each post-mortem cathode, and the vanadium valence calculated from the fitting of the spectra. “C” indicates charge and “D” indicates discharge.

Sample	Raw spectrum %	C-4.3 V spectrum %	Vanadium valence (electrochemical curves)	Vanadium valence (XANES)
Raw	100(5)	0(5)	-	3.8(1)
C-3.6 V	85(5)	15(5)	3.91	3.9(1)
C-3.9 V	40(5)	60(5)	4.14	4.2(1)
C-4.15 V	7(5)	93(5)	4.42	4.4(1)
C-4.3 V	0(5)	100(5)	4.53	4.5(1)
D-3.65 V	43(5)	57(5)	4.23	4.2(1)
D-3.52 V	100(5)	0(5)	4.1	3.8(1)
D-2.8 V	100(5)	0(5)	4.0	3.8(1)

4. Conclusions

To understand the electrochemical sodium extraction/insertion mechanism in mixed valence compounds, the starting oxidation state of the phase and the quantity or contribution of each valence state must be first thoroughly characterized. This study employs a variety of methods including XRD, NMR, XANES and a double titration to show the $V^{+3.8}$ oxidation state of $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{2x}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$, that corresponds to a 80% of V^{+4} leading to the $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_{1.6}(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{1.4}$ phase. *Post mortem* or *ex situ* XRD and XANES is then used to illustrate that the sodium extraction/insertion mechanism is a solid solution mechanism (at least in the equilibrated cathode) and that mainly the V^{+4} valence is electrochemically active transforming to V^{+5} . The V^{+3} component of the original cathode remains unchanged during electrochemical cycling in the 2.8 – 4.3 V range. *Post Mortem* analysis also indicates an anisotropic

evolution of the lattice parameter during charge, with a decreasing and c increasing, and the sodium-ion channels also contract in a (and b) and expand in c . Furthermore, the sodium extraction seems to occur preferentially from a particular site (Na(1)).

This study illustrates how XANES spectra can be analyzed using a combination of the completely charged and discharged samples, with the linear combinations of these represented in the intermediate states. These detailed structural studies establish the groundwork required to truly understand the sodium extraction/insertion mechanisms and to develop the best cathode materials from this family.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Bond lengths and Vanadium octahedral angles for raw and 4.1 V *Post Mortem* samples. Points during charge/discharge where post mortem electrodes were extracted. XANES spectra of the raw sample and the corresponding fit “This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.”

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Chem. Mater.

The electrochemical Na extraction/insertion of $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_7(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}$

A $\text{V}^{+3.8}$ cathodic material belonging to the $\text{Na}_3\text{V}_2\text{O}_7(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{F}_{3-2x}/\text{C}$ family has been prepared for sodium-ion batteries. Both, the vanadium oxidation state and the Na insertion/extraction pathway have been determined by using several techniques as high-resolution synchrotron XRD, XAS, ^{23}Na and ^{19}F NMR, a double titration method and electrochemical measurements.

